

Importance of vegetables plant species mentioned in the Holy Quran and Ahadith's books

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Received on: 15-01-2022

Accepted on: 18-02-2022

Abstract

Vegetables are one of the first-born foods known to man. Vegetables are the natural essential food of human. They contain considerable amounts of crucial nutrients in a rational proportion. Holy Quran is one of the reference books describing the significance of plants used for diverse diseases in many verses. In observation of the significance of this study widespread data was collected from Holy Quran and Ahadith's books; Current outcomes confined to several higher plant species are: *Allium cepa* L, *Allium sativum* L. *Cucumis sativus* L. *Lagenaria siceraria*, *Lagenaria siceraria* L. and *Hordeum vulgare* L. consequences were scientifically organized by alphabetical order of botanic names observed by English name, family, parts used, medicinal uses and references mentioned from Holy Quran and Ahadith. There are numerous verses in Quran talking about the vegetables, including; onions, garlic, zinger, barley, kadoo etc. What has been cited in the Quran is what researchers have done over the time, since the Quran is governed by logic. While we do not know the causes for various effects in the Quran, we consider it as the substance.

Keywords: vegetables, plant, Holy Quran, Ahadith's, species

Introduction

Vegetables are very important part of plants that are eaten as food by humans, animals and birds. Vegetables are perennial or annual agricultural crops, with definite parts like as leaves, roots, flowers, stalk and fruit that can be used completely, raw or cooked (Marwat, 2008; Warsewicz et al.,2021). Vegetables are those herbaceous plants whose parts are consumed as secondary food or important dishes and they may be fragrant, harsh or tasteless. Plants are a crucial constituent of the world. They are very essential for human diet in item of

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nutrient compounds namely as vitamins, dietary fiber, and non-nutritive molecules (flavonoids, bio-active peptides, phenolic etc.). These nutrient and non-nutrient compounds decrease the threat of chronic diseases for example cancers, cardiovascular, obesity and diabetes (Barba et al., 2014). The nutrient contents of many kind of vegetables differ much and they are not main source of glucose related to fiber nutrients which form the bulk of nutrition consumed, then comprise minerals, proteins, amino acids as well as antioxidants. Vegetables are involved in meals mostly for their nutritional values but some are earmarked for sickening and recovery because of their medicinal properties (Mensah *et al.*, 2008).

The Holy Quran is a divine book more than 1400 years old with a total of 6600 verses allocating with several features of regular life, about 1000 of those verses are of a scientific nature. There are more than 900 verses in the Holy Quran that can be interrelated to new scientific discoveries, which miraculously are said not to controvert the evidences as we now understand them (Bucaille, 1987). The Holy Quran evaluates various scientific subjects for example biology, astronomy, embryology, geology, archaeology and genetics. In the early Islamic era, the literature of Hadith or sunah had collected a number of sayings of the Prophet under a group called the Prophetic Medication (El-Gozeiha, 1990; Khafagi et al., 2006). Many plants are mentioned in both the Hadith and Prophetic Medicine due to their valuable nature as natural cures for the controlling of simple sicknesses like throat, headache, sore and fever and for improving foods and common health and fitness (El-Batanony, 1986). So, numerous books have been published to number the plants declared as part of the Prophetic Medicine practice or Hadith (El-Gozeiha, 1990).

The present study goals to record the scientific names of plants revealed in the Holy Quran, to relate them to their taxonomic, orders, families and genera and to list the verses and surahs where a distinctive plant or a plant-related keyword like plants, trees, grains, herbs, cultivars, fruits, seeds, ornamentals and gardens is cited. Several scientific topics such as seed germination, biodiversity, physiology, genetics and uses of plants are also bid with the clarification of the Holy Quran.

Specific plants refer to in the Holy Quran were possibly cited to specify holy plants such as grapes, fig date palm, olive; or aroma plants such as zinger, chamfer and basil and also nutritious plants such as zinger, onion lentils, seeds of black mustard and garlic. About 22 plants belong to 17 families were mentioned in the Holy Quran. Higher plants exposed as well as *Phoenix dactylifer*, *Panica granatum*, *Ficus carica*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Dryobalanops camphora*, *Salvadora persica*, *Citrulus colocynthis*, *Cucumis sativus*, *Cucurbita pepo*, *Allium sativum*, *A. cepa*, *Zizyphus spina-christi*, *lens esculents*, *Musa sapientum*, *Hordeum vulgare*, *Triticum vulgare*, *Trifolium*, *Brassica nigra* and *Tamarix*.

Onion

Allium cepa L. is one of the oldest plants cultivated throughout the world and belonging to the family of Alliaceae (Gurushizde et al., 2007). Onions give vital nutritional value to the human diet and have medicinal properties and are mainly used for their distinctive flavor of other foods.

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Surah al-Baqarah, Verse #. 61

وإذ قلتم يا موسى لن نصبر على طعام واحد فادع لنا ربك يخرج لنا مما تنبت الأرض من بقلها وقثائها وفومها وعدسها وبصلها ۗ قال أتستبدلون الذي هو أدنى بالذي هو خير ۗ اهبطوا مصرا فإن لكم ما سألتم ۗ وضرب عليهم الذلة والمسكنة وباءوا بغضب من الله ۗ ذلك بأنهم كانوا يكفرون بآيات الله ويقتلون النبيين بغير الحق ۗ ذلك بما عصوا وكانوا يعتدون 2:61

And (remember) when you said, "O Mûsâ (Musa)! we cannot endure one kind of food. So invoke your Lord for us to bring forth for us of what the earth grows, its herbs, its cucumbers, its Fûm (wheat or garlic), its lentils and its onions." He said, "Would you exchange that which is better for that which is lower?"

Sahih al-Bukhari (5452)

حدثنا علي بن عبد الله، حدثنا أبو صفوان عبد الله بن سعيد، أخبرنا يونس، عن ابن شهاب، قال حدثني عطاء، أن جابر بن عبد الله رضى الله عنهما . زعم عن النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم قال " من أكل ثوما أو بصلا فليعتزلنا، أو ليعتزل مسجدنا

"Reported Jabir bin 'Abdullah: (R.A.) the Prophet said, "Whoever has eaten garlic or onion should keep away from us or should keep away from our mosque"
(Sunan Abi Dawud 3829)

حدثنا إبراهيم بن موسى، أخبرنا ح، وحدثنا حيوة بن شريح، حدثنا بقرية، عن بحير، عن خالد، عن أبي زياد، خيار بن سلمة أنه سأل عائشة عن البصل، فقالت إن آخر طعام أكله رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم طعام فيه بصل

"Narrated Aisha, Ummul Mu'minin (R.A.): Khalid (R.A.) said: Abu Ziyad Khiyar ibn Salamah (R.A.) asked Aisha (R.A.) about onions. She replied: The last food which the Apostle of Allah (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) ate was some which contained onions"

Garlic

Allium sativum L. is a bulbous herb, it has a tall, round stem, erect flowering. The plant has pink florets that bloom in mid to late summer. The medicinally used as the bulb. The leaves are flat, long and linear. Garlic bulb is stated that to comprise S-methyl-L-cysteine, allinase, volatile oil, alliin, and sulfoxide. It is rich in vitamins like rniacine, iboflavin and thiamine (Tyagi et al., 2013).

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(Verse #. 61• Surah Al Baqarah):

وإذ قلتم يا موسى لن نصبر على طعام واحد فادع لنا ربك يخرج لنا مما تنبت الأرض من بقلها وقتائها وفومها وعدسها وبصلها ۗ قال أتستبدلون الذي هو أدنى بالذي هو خير ۗ اهبطوا مصرا فإن لكم ما سألتم ۗ وضربت عليهم الذلة والمسكنة وباءوا بغضب من الله ۗ ذلك بأنهم كانوا يكفرون بآيات الله ويقتلون النبيين بغير الحق ۗ ذلك بما عصوا وكانوا يعتدون

“And when you said O’ Moses We will not have patience or We will not endure on food (of) one (kind) so you pray for us (to) your Lord he brings out for us whatever sprouts or germinates (in) the earth of its vegetables or herbs and its cucumbers and its garlic and its lentils and its onions” (Rafai, 1990).

Sunan Abi Dawud 3827

حدثنا عباس بن عبد العظيم، حدثنا أبو عامر عبد الملك بن عمرو، حدثنا خالد بن ميسرة، - يعني العطار - عن معاوية بن قره، عن أبيه، أن النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم نهي عن هاتين الشجرتين وقال " من أكلهما فلا يقربن مسجدا " . وقال " إن كنتم لا بد آكليهما فأميئوهما طبخا " . قال يعني البصل والثوم

“Narrated Mu'awiyah ibn Qurrah (R.A.): the Apostle of Allah (peace_be_upon_him) forbade these two plants (i.e. garlic and onions) and he said: He who eats them should not come near our mosque. If it is necessary to eat them, make them dead by cooking, that is, onions and garlic”

Cucumber

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativa* L.), is considered as an important vegetable for fresh feeding crops internationally and belong to the family of Cucurbitaceae. It is a rich source of minerals antioxidants and vitamins (Hao et al., 2019). Its consumption commonly helps to increase metabolism and recover immunity (Sallam et al., 2021).

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(Sahih al-Bukhari 5440)

حدثنا عبد العزيز بن عبد الله، قال حدثني إبراهيم بن سعد، عن أبيه، عن عبد الله بن جعفر بن أبي طالب . رضى الله عنهما . قال رأيت النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم يأكل الرطب بالقتاء .

“Narrated 'Abdullah (R.A.) bin Ja'far bin Abi Talib (R.A.): I saw Allah's Apostle (Sallallaho Alayhi Wassallam) eating fresh dates with cucumber”

Sunan Abi Dawud 3903)

حدثنا محمد بن يحيى بن فارس، حدثنا نوح بن يزيد بن سيار، حدثنا إبراهيم بن سعد، عن محمد بن إسحاق، عن هشام بن عروة، عن أبيه، عن عائشة، رضى الله عنها قالت أرادت أُمِّي أن تسمني لدخولي على رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم فلم أقبل عليها بشيء مما تريد حتى أطعمتني القثاء بالرطب فسمنت عليه كأحسن السمن

“Reported Aisha, Ummul Mu'minin (R.A.): my mother intended to make me fat to send me to the (house of) the Apostle of Allah (Sallallaho Alayhi Wassallam). But nothing which she desired benefited me till she gave me cucumber with fresh dates to eat. Then I became very fat”

Calabash

Calabash (*Lagenaria siceraria*), is commonly known as bottle gourd and it's a member of the Family Cucurbitacea. It is cultivated as an annual monoecious, energetic creeper species. *Lagenaria siceraria* fruits are conventionally used for its cardio protective, diuretic , general tonic, antidote to certain poisons, scorpion strings, aphrodisiac, and substitute cleansing and cooling effects. It remedies pain, fever and ulcers and used for pectoral cough and other respiratory diseases specially syrup ready from the caring fruits (Minocha, 2015). The pulp of the fruit is deliberated cool, diuretic, anti-bilious and helpful in coughs and as cure to definite poisons (Van Wyk, 2011).

(As-Saaffat, Verse # 146):

وانبتنا عليه شجرة من يقطي

“And We caused a plant of gourd to grow over him”

(Sahih al-Bukhari 2092)

حدثنا عبد الله بن يوسف، أخبرنا مالك، عن إسحاق بن عبد الله بن أبي طلحة، أنه سمع أنس بن مالك . رضى الله عنه . يقول إن خياطاً دعا رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم لطعام صنعه، قال أنس بن مالك فذهبت مع رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم إلى ذلك الطعام، فقرب إلى رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم خبزاً ومرقاً فيه دباء وقديد، فرأيت النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم يتبع الدباء من حوالى القصعة . قال . فلم أزل أحب الدباء من يومئذ .

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“Reported Anas bin Malik (R.A.): a tailor invited the Prophet (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) to a meal which he had prepared and I went along with the Prophet (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam). The tailor presented barley bread and soup containing gourd and cured meat. I saw the Prophet (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) picking the pieces of gourd from around the dish and since then I have kept on liking gourd” (Ghaznavi, 2000)

- “Anas bin Malik (R.A.) reported: a tailor invited Allah's Messenger (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) to a meal which he had prepared. Anas bin Malik (R.A.) said: I went along with Allah's Messenger (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) to that feast. He presented to Allah's Messenger (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) barley bread and soup containing pumpkin and sliced pieces of meat. Anas (R.A.) said: I saw Allah's Messenger (Sallallahu Alayhi Wassallam) going after the pumpkin round the dish, so I have always liked the pumpkin since that day” (A'zami and Nadvi, 1985)

Ginger

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe), which belongs to the Zingiberaceae family and has been normally used as a flavor and an herbal remedy for a long period (Han et al., 2013). Ginger root is used to reduce and treat some collective infections, for example colds, headaches, emesis and nausea. Various compounds in ginger have been recognized, such as terpene and phenolic compounds. The phenolic compounds are mostly gingerols, paradols and shogaols which account for the several bio-activities of ginger. Furthermore, collecting studies have proved that ginger owns the potential to inhibit and succeed numerous diseases, such as respiratory disorders, neuro-degenerative diseases, obesity, cardiovascular, diabetes mellitus, nausea and emesis (Townsend et al., 2013).

(Surah Ad-Dahr Chapter # 76, Verse # 17):

ويسقون فيها كأسا كان مزاجها زنجبيلا ۝

“And they will be given to drink there of a cup (of wine) mixed with *Zanjabil* (ginger)”.

Ahadith:

“Recited 'Abdullah bin 'Umar the Prophet ordered (Muslims) to give one Sa' of dates or one Sa' of **barley** as Zakat-ul-Fitr. The people rewarded two Mudds of wheat as equal to that”. (Book [#25](#), Hadith [#583](#))

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“Narrated Abu Said Al-Khudri: In the life-time of Allah's Apostle, we used to give one Sa' of food (edible things) as Sadaqat-ul-Fitr (to the poor). Our food used to be either of **barley**, raisins (dried grapes), cottage cheese or dates”. (Book [#25](#), Hadith [#586](#))

“Described Sahl bin Sad: There was a woman amongst us who had a farm and she used to sow Silq (a kind of vegetable) on the edges of streams in her farm. On Fridays she used to pull out the Silq from its roots and put the roots in a utensil. Then she would put a handful of powdered **barley** over it and cook it. The roots of the Silq were a substitute for meat. After finishing the Jumua prayer we used to greet her and she would give us that food which we would eat with our hands, and because of that meal, we used to look forward to Friday”. (Book [#13](#), Hadith [#60](#))

Conclusion

The current statement is considered to be a speedy scientific reference for Botanist expert both basic and applied features of plant research studying botany. This message may source the systematic information of plants discovered in the Quran fourteen century ago, may boost vital medicinal exploration of most of those plants, if not really occurs for any of them, may compare botanical lighting the Holy Quran or may represent another plant topic to the list of significant neutral topics educated from the Holy book.

In conclusion, understanding the Holy Quran is wonderful and enhances numerous features of biology such as germination, systematic, anatomy and diversity. Also, varied uses of plants for food and forage, common medicine, shelter and shadow and for daily life is stated clearly in more than one verse in the Holy Quran. The botanical journey from several verses and surahs through Quran can be a multidimensional trip.

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Reference : Sahih al-Bukhari (5452)

(Sunan Abi Dawud 3829)

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Sunan Abi Dawud 3827

(Sahih al-Bukhari 5440)

Sunan Abi Dawud 3903)

(As-Saaffat, Chapter # 37, Verse # 146):

(Sahih al-Bukhari 2092)

(Surah Ad-Dahr Chapter # 76, Verse # 17):

(Book #25, Hadith #583)

(Book #25, Hadith #586

#13, Hadith #60)